

**THE CONCENTRATION OF ORGANOPHOSPHATE ESTERS FIRE RETARDANTS
IN SOILS FROM CAR DISMANTLING SITES IN DELTA STATE**

BY

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SEPTEMBER, 2022

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(FOS/18/19/252079)

INDUSTRIAL CHEMISTRY UNIT

**SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY, FACULTY OF SCIENCE,
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DECLARATION

I, Mossa Daniel Ndudi with the matriculation number FOS/18/19/252079, hereby declare that this project research work titled "**THE CONCENTRATION OF ORGANOPHOSPHATE ESTERS FIRE RETARDANTS IN THE SOILS FROM CAR DISMANTLING SITES IN DELTA STATE**" was carried out by me, and all the literature used or quoted therein have been acknowledged by proper citation and referencing, and will be submitted to the Department of Chemistry, Delta state University Abraka for the award of B.Sc Degree in Industrial Chemistry

MOSSA, Daniel Ndudi.

Date

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project work was carried out by MOSSA, Daniel Ndudi, FOS/18/19/252079, of the department of Chemistry (Industrial Chemistry unit) Delta State University, Abraka .In partial fulfilment of the requirements for the Award of Bachelor of Science (B.Sc) degree in Industrial Chemistry.

Prof C.M.A Iwegbue
(Project Supervisor)

Date

Prof (Mrs) P.O Agbaire
(Head of Department)

Date

External Examiner

Date

DEDICATION

This Research project is dedicated to God almighty and to my lovely mother late (Mrs) Veronica Ossai of blessed memory and my siblings, Madu Akpubor, Azubike Mgbonyebi, Uche Mossa, and my friends Obanuchem Jeffery, Enudi Moses, Ezute Reuben etc for their love and support.

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ABSTRACT

The aim this research is to determine the concentration of Organophosphates ester from car dismantling sites in Delta State. OPEs are one of the major constituent of herbicides, pesticides, insecticides and nerve gas. Organophosphate pesticides (OPs) have extensive applications in agriculture, horticulture, pest control, plastic making, flame retardants and for several household applications. OPs are the ester forms of phosphoric acid, usually considered as safe for agriculture use due to their relatively fast degradation rates. Acute or chronic exposure to OPs can produce varying levels of toxicity in humans, animals, plants, and insects. Through the optimization of extraction, purification, and determination parameters, a reliable and convenient analytical method, the concentration of 13 organophosphate esters in soils of car dismantling within the study area was simultaneously determined. The method is based on one-step extraction and purification by accelerated solvent extraction and analysis by High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) coupled with electrospray triple quadrupole mass spectrometry (ESI-MS/MS, API 2000). As compared to other methods, this proposed method was simple and time and solvent saving. The method was successfully applied to analyze organophosphate esters in soil samples collected from Delta state, Nigeria. Thirteen organophosphate esters were detected in all of the soil samples which indicated that the soil of car dismantling site in Delta State have been contaminated and polluted by organophosphate esters. The human health risk of organophosphate esters (OPEs) in the soils of Different location in delta state, Nigeria was assessed in this study. Ten soil samples were collected and analyzed, and \sum OPE concentrations varied from 1.06 to 6.55 ng/g -dry weight (dw). OPE concentrations in some of the sites are high, but in the others are low. Compared with other studies, OPE pollution levels are higher than farmland soils but are similar to other urban soils. Tris-(2-chloroethyl) phosphate (TCEP) is the most important carcinogen, tris-(1-chloro-2-propyl) phosphate (TCPP), 2-ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate (EHDPP) and tri-iso-butyl phosphate (TiBP) are the most important non-carcinogens. OPE concentrations are the most sensitive parameter that contributed the largest to the total variance of risk, TCEP is the most influential variable for carcinogenic risk, and TCPP, EHDPP and TiBP are the most influential variables for non-carcinogenic risk.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

Fire retardants are mostly added or applied in most material to prevent and avert quick fire spreading on ignition. The overall amount of fire retardants produced globally especially in countries such as Asia, Europe, The United States of America etc. is around 1.8million metric tons in 2007.(Yansin *et al.*,2016).

Due to the fact that fire retardants (FRs) do not chemically bond to materials that is they are only physically attached, they can be easily released from materials into the air, they can also accumulate in environmental surfaces such as soils, water etc. and can be easily contacted by human beings. Brominated fire retardants was replaced by Organophosphate fire retardants because of their toxic effect. The Organophosphate fire retardants (OPFRs) are massively produced into the global market for the formulation of plasticizers and anti-foaming agents. They are also and mainly used as fire retardants in products and materials that humans consume and comes in contact with daily e.g, textiles, furniture, personal care products etc (Van der veen and de Boer,2012).

Global distribution characteristics of Organophosphate fire retardants indicated their long range transport (Salamo et al., 2014;Suhr Suhring *et al.*,2016a,b).The soil is a major sink for all kinds of chemicals as well as important matrices for mass exchange with food chain with bioaccumulation factors (BCFs) ranging from 128 to 4.44×10^4 ,OPFRs have a great variation in bioaccumulation potential (Hou *et al.*,2016).

Many studies have detected OPFRs in different matrices around the world which includes Soils (Cui et al.,2007;Matsukami et al.,2015;Wan et al.,2016).Water (Bacaloni et al.,2007;Meyer and Bester,2004;Rodil et al.,2012).The Atmosphere (Clark et al.,2017;Luo et al.,2016;Yang et al.,2014) and food (Zhang et al.,2016).

The major reservoir and hydrophobic organic compound interchange is the soil (Yadav et al.,2018a). Irrigation with sewage and the application of biosolids to agricultural lands can introduce impressive OPFRs to soil ecosystem (Miller et al.,2016).As an organic compound, OPFRs can readily adsorb into the soil particles due to their hydrophobicity (LogKow)(Pang et al.,2013). Previous studies have addressed the adverse effects of Organophosphate esters, they includes

- Carcinogenicity (Wei et al.,2015)
- Genotoxicity (Shen et al.,2018;Su et al.,2014)
- Cardiotoxicity (McGee et al., 2013).
- Dermatitis (Camarassa and Serra-Baldrich,1992;McGee et al.,2013)
- Reproductive toxicity (Camarasa and Serra-Baldrich, 1992;Li et al.,2015).

In recent years, Organophosphate esters have been receiving even more environmental attention knowing fully well that several halogenated fire retardant (HFRs) were listed as persistent organic pollutants (POPs) (UNEP,2017),and that several OPEs have been proposed as replacement or chemical substitute for these phase-out HFRs (Iqbal et al.,2017).

There is a great significance and difference between the physiochemical properties such as octanol-water partition coefficient (Kow) ,water solubility and vapour pressure of OPFRs.(Reemtsma et al.,2008;Van der veen and de Boer 2012).Because of the fact that fire retardants are not chemically bonded to products, but are only physically attached, they can easily be released into the environment through volatilization, abrasion or leaching during the production, use and disposal of treated products (Marklund et al.,2015;Van den Eede et al.,2011).

There is growing evidence of the existence occurrence of OPFRs in various environmental media as well as human urine and human breast milk (Cristale and Lacorte,2013;Hoff Hoffman et al.,2014;Markl Marklund et al.,2005;Sundk Sundkvist et al.,2010;Van den Eede et al.,2013).

The phosphorus compound when heated react to form a polymeric form of phosphorus acid, this acid causes a char layer shielding the burning material from oxygen and thus slowing down the reaction (Van der veen and de Boer 2012).

1.2 Statement of problem

Polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) were banned to be used as fire retardant and plasticizers and consequently replace by Organophosphate esters owing to the facts that PBDEs are very toxic and therefore harmful to man.

OPFRs which was thought of as a better substitute for PBDEs have been discovered to be even more toxic and harmful to man and it's ecosystem, and hence more dangerous than PBDEs.

1.31 General objective of the study

The general objective of the study is to determine the occurrence and concentration of Organophosphate esters in the soil around car dismantling sites.

1.32 Specific objective of the study

The specific objectives of the study are:

- ★ To determine the concentration of organophosphate esters in soils from car dismantling sites within delta state
- ★ To determine the risk associated with exposure to Organophosphate fire retardants in soils from car dismantling site around Delta state.

1.4 Significance of the study

This study provides information that is necessary for designing monitoring program for organophosphate fire retardant from car dismantling sites in delta state and environmental quality management

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Organophosphate Esters

With the phase out of polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) as fire retardants, the demand for an alternate fire retardant increased. Organophosphate ester (OPEs) which are well known are recognized as substitutes for polybrominated diphenyl ethers and have been extensively used world wide, and the usage has been on the increasing side with annual global consumption of 500,000 tons in 2011, 680,000 tons in 2015, and 816,000 tons in 2018 (Abademosi *et al.*, 2021, Hou *et al.*, 2016). OPEs are used globally especially in industrial and consumer products (Calson *et al.*, 2000; Marklund *et al.*, 2005a, 2005b; Salthammer *et al.*, 2003).

Over 150 years ago, since the phase out of PBDEs, organophosphate esters which are organic ester derivatives of phosphorous, have been used as insecticides, herbicides, nerve agents, and flame retardants. (vander Veen and de Boer, 2012).

Phosphorus is one of the most effective elements for retarding fire. (USEPA, 1976). These land-based sources result in environmental temporal stocks of OPEs reaching coastal and off-shore areas due to atmospheric transport and deposition (Casal *et al.*, 2018; Casal-jimenez *et al.*, 2018)

It has been detected and found in various environmental matrices which includes but is not limited to sediments, dust, human, water, air etc. (Bacaloni *et al.*, 2007, Cao *et al.*, 2021; Li *et al.*, 2014; Marklund *et al.*, 2003, 2005a; Moller *et al.*, 2012; regnery & Puttmann, 2010).

Organophosphate compounds are the major components that are used in the manufacture of herbicides, pesticides and insecticides. They are also the main components of nerve gas (Adeyinka and Pierre, 2018) organophosphate pesticides (OPs) constitute a group of biogenic and synthetic compounds which contain C-P linkage that is chemically and thermally inert and are highly resistant to hydrolysis induced by heat, protolytic degradation and chemical composition

as compared to similar Ops containing more reactive S-P, O-P or N-P linkage.(Greaves and letcher, 2017; O'Brien,2016; Kumar, U padhay, Wasit, Singh and Kaur, 2013).

The basic structure of organophosphate pesticides consist of terminal oxygen connected to phosphorus by a double bond i.e a phosphoryl group, two lipophilic group bonded to the phosphorus and a leaving group bonded to the phosphorus which is often in halide (kumar *et al.*, 2013).

Organophosphorus compounds are widely used for agriculture, horticulture, pest control purpose (Adeyinka and pierre 2018; singh and Prasad 2018; Ballantyne and Marrs, 2017; Yadav et al ., 2014).

Organophosphate ester have many industrial application and utilization and these includes flame retardancy plasticizers and anti-foaming agents in a variety of industries, such as plastics, furniture, textile, electrical and electronics, construction, vehicle and petroleum industries (Marklund *et al.*, 2003).

Many of the OPs are frequently present as additives rather than chemically bonded to diverse materials, such as furniture, textile coatings, upholstery, electronics, paints, polyvinyl chloride (PVC) plastics, polyurethane foams (PUFs), lubricants and hydraulic fluids, resulting in an easy release to different environmental compartments via volatilization, leaching and/or abrasion (Carlsson *et al.*, 2000; Salthammer *et al.*, 2003; Marklund *et al.*, 2005c).

2.1.2 Exposure Risk and Toxicity of Organophosphate Pesticide

Chronic exposure to OPs can yield varying level of toxicity in humans, animals, plants, and insects. Most of the organophosphate pesticides inhibits acetylcholinesterase activity which affects the nervous system in terrestrial fauna as well as those in aquatic fauna (Muhammed, 2017; King and Aaron 2015).

They are the cause of neuroteratogenicity and genotoxicity including ecological and adverse environmental impacts (Sun et al., 2016; Pinkes, Turgeman, Tayel and Yanai 2015). Organophosphate pesticides poses potential risk to metabolic, neurological, endocrine, hepatorenal disorder psychiatric manifestations and neuritis (Kumar et al., 2016).

OPs are also linked to increase in bladder cancer and leukemia in farmers followed by genotoxic effects, and have been known to adversely affect the photosynthesis (Zobiolo, Kremer, de Oliveira, and Constantin 2012; Kielak sempruch, Mioduszezwska, Klocek, and Lescyn'ski, 2011), Plant mineral nutrition (Zobiolo et al., 2010; Zobiolo, Kremer, Oliveira and Constantin, 2011), carbon metabolism (Ding. Reddy, Zablotowicz, Ballaloui, Bruns, 2011; Zobiolo et al., 2011). Phochemical reaction (Vivancas et al., 2011), chlorophyll biosynthesis (Serra et al., 2013), fatty acids synthesis, amino acids synthesis, nitrogen metabolism (Zobiolo et al., 2010) and oxidative stress (Vagi, Petsas, Pavlaki, Smaragdaki, and Kostopouloe, 2018; Stauber, Chariton and Apte 2016; Filimomova, Goncalves, Marques, DeFroch and Goncatvos, 2016; Yamiccari, Tambussi, Istilart and Castro, 2012).

The reactive oxygen species are a part of normal metabolism of the cell as well, but the deleterious effect of the same materializes when the balance between the ROS (reactive oxygen species produced and ROS scavenged is disturbed upon damage to this equilibrium, accumulation of ROS can affect cell growth and survival (Gomes et al., 2014). OPs have also been found to effects non target plants causing inhibition of chlorophyll synthesis as well as protein and carbohydrate synthesis.

2.2 Types of Organophosphate Esters

Based on their different functional groups OPEs, can be classified as

- i. Halogenated
- ii. Non halogenated OPEs (Vander veen and de Boer, 2012).

Halogenated OPEs includes, tris(1,3-dichloro-2-isopropyl)phosphate. TDCIPP and tris(2-chloroethyl)phosphate. TCEP, have been prohibited and restricted in children products and residential upholstered furnitures in the USA (Lalovic et al., 2004). In the EU, restriction over the use of TDCIPP and TCEP have also be issued because of their carcinogenic potency (ECHA, 2008a; ECHA, 2008b). the restriction of halogenated OPEs have prompted the development of non-halogenated OPEs which includes tris(2 – Butoxyethyl) phosphate. TBOEP, tris(n-butyl)phosphate. TMBP and triphenyl phosphate. TPHP.

Non- halogenated OPEs can be rapidly released into their surrounding environment because they are not chemically bonded to host materials (Vander Ven and de Boer, 2012). Various aquatic environment across the world holds considerable levels of non halogenated OPEs (Andersen et al ., 2004; Cristale et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2015).

It can also be classified into three groups. Namely; chlorinated alkyl, non- chlorinated alkyl and aryl phosphate. Chlorinated alkyl phosphate (Cl-OPFRs) includes tris(2-chloroisopropyl) phosphate. (TCIPP), tris (2- chloroethyl) phosphate (TCEP) and tris(1,3-dichloro-2-isopropyl) phosphate. (TDCIPP) have been used as FRs in both polyurethane (PUFs) and rigid, wood, anti –corrosive coatings, polyesters, resins, textile, plastics, electronics and floor – sealing materials (Meeker and Stapleton, 2010 ; Vander veen, and de Boer, 2012; Wang et al., 2017).

Non- chlorinated alkyl phosphate (NCI-OPFRs) such as triethyl phosphate. TEP, tri(Isobutyl) phosphate (TIBP), tributyl phosphate. TBP, tris(2- butoxyethyl) phosphate and tris (2-ethylhexyl) phosphate. TEHP, have been used as additive plasticizers in board polishes /waxes, vinyl resins (Kim et al ., 2019) glues and decorations materials such as PVC wallpaper, non-woven wallpaper and black board (Wang et al ., 2017).

Lastly Aryl phosphate (Aryl-OPFRs), they includes tricresyl phosphate. TCP, triphenyl phosphate. TPHP, 2 – ethylhexyldiphenyl phosphate. EHDP. They have been used extensively as plasticizers in PVC application, polymers, plastics, electronics, equipment, furniture and construction (Cristale et al., 2012 Maris et al ., 2020).

2.3 Methods of Detection

Organophosphate esters are mainly detected through the following techniques.

1. Gas chromatography- Mass spectrometry (GC-MS) (Lu et al., 2014; Garcia-lopez et al., 2007; Ma et al.,2013; Aragon et al., 2012)
2. Liquid chromatography- Mass spectrometry (LC-MS) (Chu and Letcher 2015; Guo et al., 2016; Long et al., 2017).

LC-MS demonstrate excellence sensitivity and specificity for OPE analysis, but the matrix interference has hampered the application of LC-MS especially using electrospray ionization (ESI) source (Chu and Letcher 2015).

GC-MS has a high selectivity and sensitivity and is very suitable for analyzing organic compounds in complex matrix.

2.4 Sources and Transfer Routes of OPEs in Agriculture

Because of the worldwide presence of OPEs in agro-foods, many questions related to their sources, entry and transfer routes of these compounds have arisen. agro-foods can be contaminated collectively through the following three routes

- Crop such as rice, vegetable and fruits; livestock such as cattle, chicken and pigs and aquatic products including fishes, shrimp and mussels that can absorb OPEs through the contaminated agri-environment such as farmland soils, water, air and sediments, which results in OPEs accumulating subsequently in the final agro-products.
- Livestock can ingest agriculture inputs that's are contaminated for example meat, milk and eggs; and

Agro foods can also be contaminated by OPEs during post-harvest and industrial processing such as storage and package, due to their presence in materials used in these processes (Ding et al.,2018;Li et al.,2019a;Poma et al.,2018;Zhang et al.,2020a;Zhang et al;2016).

2.4.1. Agri-environment

Agri-environment including soil, water, air and sediments are the most discussed potential source of OPEs in agro-foods.

Organophosphate esters can easily escape into the environment during all stages of the OPE-containing products life cycle from manufacturing to use, disposal and recycling (Zhang et al.,2021a)

Plants

Studies which have confirmed that OPEs can be absorbed and accumulated into plants from soils, water and air have increased in number (Hyland et al.,2015;Wang et al.,2021b;Zhang et al.,2016).Root uptake from soil or water and foliar uptake from air or from deposited particles are the main routes through which OPEs enter plants. Concentration of OPEs in plant rhizosphere soils were less than those in bulk soils, which demonstrated depletion by uptake or enhanced degradation by plant(Wang et al.,2021b).

Point sources of OPEs could have widespread effects on surrounding including cropland soils, water and sediments which resulted in the accumulation of TCEP and TCIPP in tree barks surrounding the manufacturing facilities (Ren et al.,2019)

Because of the use of sewage sludge and manure as fertilizer or soil conditioner on agricultural soils, while effluents from waste water treatment plants (WWTPs) are used for irrigation; contaminants can easily be transported to the soil and the risk of introducing OPEs into crops is therefore introduced (Eggen et al.,2013)

Animals

Studies have been conducted to study the influence of the ambient environment on biota or animal in an agricultural environment such as air and river water (He et al.,2019).

Yet there is limited information on the sources and transmission of route of accumulation of OPEs by domestic livestock in agri-environment. Results showed that great concentration of TCIPP, TDCIPP And TCEP in Bio-resources materials such as recycles waste food, dried paper sludge and paper sludge ash, also potentially transferred contaminants into animal derived foods via animal breeding (Rigby et al.,2021)

Aquatic biota

Aquatic environments are major sinks for OPE's processes which transports OPEs through the atmosphere into the water to be deposited as sediments is an important sources of OPEs for many aquatic organisms (Hale et al.,2003;Igbal et al.,2017).

domestic sewage and wastewaters from factories, construction sites, and pavements also contribute to he accumulation of OPEs in aquatic environments (Henriquez-Hamandez et al.,2017).

Emission from fishing boats, riverine discharge, extensive local aquaculture activities and effluent from nearby industrial and economic zones of waste water treatment plants increases the tendency of bioaccumulation and biomagnification of OPEs in biota (Bekcle et al.,2019).

Distribution of OPEs in fish was investigated and results shows that OPEs might primarily be absorbed from water through the gills and epithelial tissue rather than through food web biomagnification (Kim et al.,2011;malarvannam et al.,2015;sundkvist et al.,2010).

2.4.2 Agricultural Inputs

Residual OPEs in raw ingredients and packaging materials such as polypropylene woven bags, might be sources of OPEs in feeds, although OPEs tends to degrade on biota, bioaccumulation of TCIPP, TCEP, AND TBOEP in ecosystems have been demonstrated (Zhao et al.,2020b).

Fishmeal which consumed one third of he global annual fish production is widely applied in the global animal farming industry, especially for agriculture (Li et al.,2018)

OPEs such as TCEP,TCIPP,TDCIPP And TBOEP as well as their transformation products, including organophosphate di ester were also detected in all fishmeal samples collected across the world with a comparable average concentration (59.3+- 92.2% ng/g dm for OPEs and 49.6+- 27.5 ng/g dm for their metabolites (Li et al.,2020).

Bio-resources materials used in Agriculture for soil improvement were a possible source of OPEs in plants, derived agro-foods, biosolids (treated sewage sludge), meat, bone meat ash, poultry litter ash, paper sludge ash, and compost-like output are commonly recycled as soil amendments .OPEs were detected in these Bio-resources materials, TCIPP was the dominant compound in biosolids and compost-like output, TCEP was found in paper sludge ash and poultry litter ash (Rigby et al.,2021)

2.4.3 Agro-foods processing

An investigation of OPEs carried out in Australia exhibited a result with lease concentration of OPEs in samples with inedible outer part such as orange, banana and egg, than those samples contacting directly with plastic packages or display trays. Although the differences is not so significant, rh the results suggestions that packaged materials or other use of the food might be a potential source of OPEs in these foods (He et al.,2018b)

In Belgium and China, concentrations of OPEs especially EHDPP which have been approved by the US food and drug administration (US-FDA),for packaging applications, were greater in processed foods like oil, meat, cheese, milk and candy, than non-processed foods. This suggest that those processed foods were contaminated during industrial processing and manipulation, whi which includes canning, packaging and drying; these processes could be a key source for the contamination of these foods(Poma et al.,2018;Zhao et al.,2019)

Similar results was reported in the united states, food packaging was suggested as source of TCPP contamination in fishes and meat (Han et al.,2019).

2.5 Effect of Organophosphate on Soil Nutrients

The interaction of organophosphate pesticides with soil depends upon the sorption value ($\log K_{ow}$), the interaction of the pesticides with soil organic, inorganic components of the molecular level are central to their bioavailability, bioaccumulation, transport and toxicity in the environment (Morton and Edwards, 2005).

Profound understanding of the soil interaction with pesticides is very important to understand the soil-pesticide minerals, soil-pesticide organic matter, soil-pesticide plants and soil fertility mechanism (Polubesova and Chefetz, 2014).

Organophosphate pesticides are known to interact on the surface of the soil mineral and the soil organic matter present in the soil (Dior, Yaron and Berkowitz, 2017; Alfonsa, German, del Carmen and Hossein, 2017; Scheuneri, 2018).

The interaction of soil to pesticides depends upon four (4) major factors which are

- Nature of solvent (mainly water)
- Nature of solute (mainly pesticides)
- Soil pH
- Soil constituents

(Gianfreda and Rao, 2008)

The stability of human health in developed and developing towns and cities is highly dependent on the status of urban soils (Simpson, 1996). Strong compaction, contamination by wastes and atmospheric depositions, loss of organic matter, changes in soil reaction, structural degradation and infection by pathogenic microorganisms are only few of the many adverse processes that affect and modify the ecological functions of soils in urban areas (Bullock and Gregory, 1991; Jim, 1993; Beyer et al., 1995; Blum, 1998).

It has been reported by many authors that heavy metals on reaching the soil remain present in the pedosphere for many years even after the removal and replacement of the pollution sources, this leads to the increase in the quantity of heavy metals in the soils of urban areas (Klein, 1972; Chen et al., 1997; Pichtel et al., 1997). However, to measure the severity of pollution not only the total heavy metal content of the soil has to be taken into consideration, but also the proportion of their mobile and bio-available forms, which are generally controlled by the texture and other physicochemical properties of soils (Brummer et al., 1986; Ma and Rao, 1997; Selim and Sparks, 2001).

2.6 Biodegradation of Organophosphate Pesticides

Organophosphate Pesticides (OPs) have been known to be greatly persistent in soils and this class includes the chlorinated derivatives of di-phenylethene, the group of hexachlorocyclohexane, the group of cyclodiene, and chlorinated hydrocarbons (Hussain, Siddique, Arshad, and Saleem, 2009; Pehkoem and Zhang, 2002; Patnaik, 2003; Menome et al., 2001).

These groups mentioned either contain P=O or P=S and since they are esters, they have many sites that are prone to hydrolysis either by microbial action or by organic amendment (Bricano, Palma and Duran 2007). The main and principal reactions involved in the microbial degradation include, Hydrolysis, Oxidation, Alkylation, and dealkylation (Singh et al., 1999).

It occurs through the hydrolysis of the bond of P-O-Alkyl and P-O-Aryl and are also considered as the most significant step in detoxification. A very large number of aquatic and soil microbes that possess the ability to degrade the pesticides and its by-product completely, have been found, whereas the pure isolates which individually possess the very said capacity to mineralize OPs is very rare. Therefore, one needs to find the natural or engineer the microbe which can degrade the OPs especially for bioremediation purpose (Caspi et al., 2012).

When a microbe possesses the ability to mineralize OPs compounds completely, it encompasses all the linked genes that are required for degradation of such compounds, most of the identified gene clusters are lined with transposable elements, revealing that these lower pathways are mobile and can adhere to the gene coding for main hydrolase enzyme (Siddavattam et al., 2003).

The first Organophosphorus degrading gene (OPD) used in the degradation of organophosphate pesticides was found in *pidiminuta*, and was shown to be present in plasmid (Serder et al., 1982).

OPD gene and its homologs are the genetic components which take part in OPs metabolism and natural degradation of organophosphate pesticides. The OPD gene product parathion hydrolase, was the first enzyme to be characterized for its ability to degrade Organophosphorus and then later organophosphate hydrolase (OPH) was characterized. The encoding gene was isolated from the large plasmids of *Brevundimonas diminuta* GM and *Sphingobium fuliginis* ATCC 27551 (Kawahara et al., 2010)

Nonhalogenated organophosphate esters can be degraded more easily than OPEs through traditional sewage treatment process (Reemtma et al., 2008). The rates of removal of nonhalogenated OPEs i.e. (TBOEP, TNBP & TPHP) ranges from 57-86%, 38-68.8%, 27-79% and 20.1-60.7% in typical waste water treatment plants (WWTPs) in Germany (Mayor and Bester, 2004), USA (Kim et al., 2017), Sweden (Marklund et al., 2005), and China (Fu et al., 2017) respectively.

In addition, organophosphate di-esters (di-alkyl phosphate) (DAPs), which includes di(n-butyl)phosphate (DNBP) and diphenyl phosphate (DPHP) (metabolites of TNBP & TPHP respectively) were widely detected in activated sludge of sewage treatment plants in the USA (Kim et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2019) and China (Fu et al., 2017; Gao et al., 2016).

The DAPs were expected to be the degradation products of OPEs based on source analysis (Fu et al.,2017).Therefore, activated sludge is considered a major degradation medium on WWTPs (Fu et al.,2017).However some humans and animal studies have clarified that the hydroxylation and other oxidation biotransformation pathways as well as the hydrolysis from OPEs to DHP, are significant for OPEs degradation (Gao et al .,2016;Hou et al.,2018;Hou et al.,2016; Vander Eede et al.,2013).

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Description of study area.

Delta state is located in the south-south geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Its coordinates are 5°30'N 6°00'E, with Asaba and Warri as the capital and center of commerce respectively. It is bordered on the northern pole by Edo state, on the eastern pole by Anambra and Rivers state, on the southern pole by Bayelsa state and lastly on the western pole by the Bight of Benin. It have a total of 25 local government areas and a total land mass of about 18,050 km², in which more than 60% is land. Other geographical features includes River Niger, River Forcados, River Escravos, River Ethiope etc.

Map of Delta State Nigeria showing the study area

(Stella *et al.*,2020)

pictorial representation of some locations visited during the course of sample collection

3.2 Categories of target OPEs

Tri-n-butyl phosphate (TNBP), tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate (TBOEP), tris(2-ethylhexyl) phosphate (TEHP) are grouped as alkyl-OPEs; TCEP, TCPP, and tris(1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate (TDCPP) are classified Cl-OPEs; TPHP, 2-ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate (EHDPP), Tri-p-tolyl phosphate (TPTP) and isodecyl diphenyl phosphate (IDPP) are aryl-OPEs; RDP and BDP are oligomeric OPEs; Tris (2,3-dibromopropyl) phosphate (TDBPP) is grouped under Br-OPEs.

3.3. Sample collection

Soil samples were collected from May to June 2020. In total, 10 soil samples were collected

across Delta State Nigeria,, covering 3 towns namely Ozoro, Oleh, and Kwale in Ugheli North, Ugheli South and Ndokwa West local governments respectively. Soil samples (1–5 cm) were collected with a stainless steel shovel after removing the surface debris (~1 cm). Soil samples were collected from multiple spots at a given location at ambient conditions. Sampling tools and glass containers (amber bottles) (muffled at 450 °C overnight) were cleaned with methanol and labelled prior to use. Samples were transported to the laboratory within 3 days of sampling, freeze-dried, homogenized, sieved (stainless-steel sieve, b2.0 mm), and stored at temperature of –20 °C until further analysis.

3.4. Sample preparation

The extraction methods for OPEs has been reported in chapter 2 above (Kim et al., 2017). Briefly, soil samples were extracted by Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE-200) and purified by passage through Oasis HLB cartridges (60 mg, 3 cm³, before instrumental analysis. Total organic carbon (TOC) content of soils was determined using elemental analyzer (EuroVector,EA3000). Detailed information on the concentrations obtained is presented in the table D1

3.5. Instrumental analysis

Thirteen OPEs were analyzed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC ; Jacio laboratories & Technologies, Warri, Delta state, Nigeria) coupled with electrospray triple quadrupole mass-spectrometry (ESI-MS/MS, API 2000; Applied Biosystems). Analytes were chromatographically separated by a Betasil C18 column (100 mm × 2.1 mm, 5 µm; Thermos). Further information on the median concentrations recorded is given in table D2

3.6 Quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC)

The regression coefficients of calibration curves (0.1–400 ng/mL) used in the quantitation of OPEs were N0.99. The limits of quantitation (LOQs) were set at the signal to noise ratio of 10 (at the lowest point of the calibration standard). TNBP, TBOEP, TCEP, TPHP, EHDPP, TPTP, IDPP, RDP, and TEHP, profound procedural blanks at trace levels (0.01–0.02ng). OPEs were not found in travel and field blank samples. Median concentrations ranges from 0.07 to 0.42 ng/g dry weight

(dw) for OPEs. Average recoveries of OPEs ranged from 65.8 to 129% in soil sample. A pure solvent (methanol) and midpoint calibration standard were injected after every five (5 q) samples to monitor for carryover of target chemicals between samples and drift in instrumental sensitivity.

3.7. Statistical data analysis

The data from the laboratory analysis were used as variable inputs for the descriptive statistics such as median, minimum and maximum in SPSS software statistical tool version 23.0.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

Table D1

4.1 Organophosphate flame retardants in soils from car dismantling sites (ng/g) dw

	DS1	DS2	DS3	DS4	DS5	DS6	DS7	DS8	DS9	DS10
TCEP	0.13	0.21	0.11	0.08	0.28	0.28	0.01	0.07	0.62	0.11
TCPP	0.13	0.07	0.73	0.09	0.13	0.14	0.18	0.05	0.39	0.08
TDCPP	0.05	0.23	0.03	0.32	0.45	0.09	0.15	0.07	0.48	0.07
TDBPP	0.17	0.20	0.03	0.29	0.23	0.10	0.18	1.66	0.17	0.06
TPHP	0.18	0.30	0.02	0.31	0.19	0.56	0.01	0.03	0.07	0.12
EHDPP	0.10	0.22	0.01	0.15	0.19	0.03	0.14	0.86	0.25	0.06
TPTP	0.10	0.13	0.78	0.10	0.10	0.06	0.01	0.04	0.29	0.48
IDPP	0.27	0.04	0.22	0.23	0.45	0.25	0.01	0.07	0.31	0.05
RDP	0.63	0.20	0.02	1.60	2.49	1.47	0.01	0.34	0.26	0.49
BDP	0.18	0.22	0.40	1.64	0.57	0.18	0.09	0.35	0.99	0.14
TNBP	0.19	0.19	0.67	1.15	0.99	0.07	0.01	0.51	0.41	0.24
TBOEP	0.53	0.09	0.01	0.40	0.42	0.16	0.17	0.32	0.80	0.23
TEHP	0.09	0.04	0.02	0.12	0.05	0.06	0.10	0.08	0.14	0.05
TOTAL	2.75	2.15	3.05	6.47	6.55	3.45	1.06	4.45	5.16	2.18

Table D1 shows that 13 different Organophosphate esters with different concentrations from different location within the study area.

Table D2**Median concentrations of the 13 Organophosphate ester analyzed (ng/g) dw**

OPEs	Minimum	Maximum	Median
TCEP	0.01	0.62	0.12
TCPP	0.05	0.39	0.13
TDCPP	0.03	0.48	0.12
TPHP	0.01	0.56	0.15
EHDPP	0.01	0.86	0.15
TPTP	0.01	0.78	0.10
IDPP	0.01	0.45	0.23
RDP	0.01	2.49	0.42
BDP	0.09	1.64	0.29
TNBP	0.01	1.15	0.33
TBOEP	0.01	0.80	0.28
TEHP	0.02	0.14	0.07
TDBPP	0.03	1.66	0.18
Total	0.30	12.02	2.57

Table D2 above show the minimum, maximum and median concentrations of the thirteen (13) Organophosphate esters found in the soils of car dismantling site in the study area.

4.2 Discussion of Results

From table D1, the value of the total concentration of the contaminant (OPEs) recorded from the 10 different location of the study ranges from 1.06 to 6.55. The highest value recorded is $<6.55>$ ng/g dw gotten from location DS5, followed by $<6.47 >$ ng/g dw from location DS4. The lowest value of concentration that was recorded is $<1.06>$ ng/g dw gotten from location DS7, followed by $<2.15>$ ng/g dw gotten from location DS2.

From table D2 Among the organophosphates esters, the highest value of median concentrations recorded is RDP $<0.42>$ ng/g dw, and it ranges from (0.01 to 2.49). It is the most abundant Organophosphate ester contaminant found in car dismantling site in the study area.

Followed by TNBP with a concentration of $<0.33>$ ng/g dw. It's range is (0.01 to 1.15)

The lowest median concentrations value recorded is TEHP $<0.07>$ ng/g dw. It's range is (0.02 to 0.14).it is the least abundant OPEs contaminants analyzed in the study area during the course of this research.

From Table D1, the contaminant with the highest value of concentration analyzed is RDP with a concentration of $<2.49>$ ng/g dw found is location DS5. Followed by TDBPP with a concentration of $<1.66>$ ng/g dw gotten from location DS8. The least concentration analyzed is TCEP from location D7,TPHP from location D7,EHDPP from location D3,TPTP from location D7, IDPP from location D7, TNBP from location D7, TBOEP from location D3 with a concentration value of $<0.01>$ ng/g dw respectively. Followed by TPHP from location D3, RDP from location D3, TEHP from location D3, with a concentration value of $<0.02>$ ng/g dw respectively.

This shows that the level of contamination of some car dismantling site is higher and greater than others,this maybe because of some factors such as

- The site or location was just recently opened.
- The location is a rural area and therefore less frequent dismantling of vehicles.
- The effect of soil erosion have washed many of them away into nearby water bodies

According to the result from analysis of the contaminants in this study is evidently clear that there is an insignificant concentration value on OPEs contaminants in location DS7 and DS3

respectively, since about nine (9) out of the thirteen (13) OPEs found are in minute quantity in the study area. They include TCEP, TPHP, EHDPP, TPTP, IDPP, TNBP, TBOEP, RDP, TEHP. Few studies have reported the occurrence of emerging aryl- and oligomeric OPEs, including CDPP, IDDP, RDP and BDP in environmental matrices (Bjornsdotter *et al.*, 2018; Christia *et al.*, 2018; Kademoglou *et al.*, 2017)

Previous studies have reported similar concentrations of TCPP in urban soils in China (15.5–16.7 ng/g dw) (Lu *et al.*, 2014) and Turkey (17.1 ng/g dw) (Kurt-Karakus *et al.*, 2018), and TCPP was the dominant compound found in these studies. However, the median concentrations of TCIPP in soils found in our study were lower than those reported in Nepal (165 ng/g dw) (Yadav *et al.*, 2018a), and a waste recycling area in China (378 ng/g dw) (Wang *et al.*, 2018b).

In addition to TCPP, aryl-OPEs such as TPHP and TMPP were found in soil samples. However, median concentrations of TMPP (0.29 ng/g dw) across China were generally lower than those reported for urban locations in China (28 ng/g dw) (Cui *et al.*, 2017a) and Nepal (230 ng/g dw) (Yadav *et al.*, 2018a) as well as in point source areas in China (46.3 ng/g dw) (Wang *et al.*, 2018b). From table D1, it is recorded that the site location with the lowest concentration of OPEs is DS7, with a range of (0.01 to 0.18 ng/g dw) which is an insignificant value.

Also from table D2, the contaminant with the lowest value among all other is TEHP with a range of (0.02 to 0.14 ng/g dw) across the ten locations visited in the area of study which is also an insignificant value.

RDP (2.49 ng/g dw), TDBPP (1.66 ng/g dw) and BDP (1.64 ng/g dw) was found in high loading, this indicates that they are originated from a similar source. Aryl OPEs such as TPTP is widely used in hydraulic fluids and engine oils (Marklund *et al.*, 2005; Takimoto *et al.*, 1999) and plastic (Poma *et al.*, 2017; Wang and Kanann 2018).

Cl-OPEs (TCEP, TCPP, TDCPP) are easily released from polyurethane (PUF) products (Ingerowski *et al.*, 2001; Stapleton *et al.*, 2009) which might explain the similarities in these chemicals

Median concentration of TNBP values exceeded 1 ngg-1 in samples from Germany (Nagorka and Ulrich, 2003), Belgium (van den Eede et al., 2011), Sweden (Bergh et al., 2011; Luongo and Östman, 2015) and Japan (Kanazawa et al., 2010; Araki et al., 2014). But the median concentration of TNBP recorded in this research project of <0.33 ng/g dw>. This may be because Germany, Belgium, Sweden and Japan, are developed countries and have been practicing frequent vehicle dismantling compared to Nigeria and in the study area.

RDP is an oligomeric phosphate ester flame retardant that is designed for use in engineered resin applications such as polyphenylene oxide alloys and PC/ABS. Because of its low volatility and high heat stability, this non-halogen flame retardant can tolerate high temperature processing required of many engineered resins.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION

5.1 DISCUSSION

For the most soluble compounds (TCEP and TCPP), their low affinity to soil and ubiquitous presence in anthropogenically affected rivers suggest that these contaminants reach Soil is composed of mineral constituents and its organic matter content is the major terrestrial environmental reservoir and one of the vital sinks for organic pollutants, such as OPEs (Cui et al.,2017)

As organic compounds, OPFRs can easily and readily adsorb into the soil particles due to their high hydrophobicity ($\log K_{ow}$)(Pangetal.,2013). TPHP and other OPFRs are major components of Fire-master 550, a flame retardant mixture commonly used in furniture foam at concentrations greater than the legacy flame retardants it replaced (Van der veen et al.,2012).

Now, these furniture foams are used in the manufacturing of some vehicle parts such a vehicle front and back seats etc. The wear and tear of vehicle parts through dismantling will release these Organophosphate contaminants into the soil environmental matrix basically by abrasion volatilization or leaching. Similarly, the less soluble compounds, such as TDCP, TPHP, and EHDPP, tend to accumulate in sediments, while the most water-soluble OPEs are transported far from their original sources. Contaminated soil poses a threat to groundwater. (Wang et al., 2015). groundwater by bank filtration. If not properly managed, the leachate from waste disposal sites can also become a source of these contaminants in groundwater. In fact, TCEP and TCPP were the most frequently detected OPEs in anthropogenically affected groundwater in Germany, and the highest OPEs concentrations ($> 100 \text{ ngL}^{-1}$) were found in groundwater polluted by percolating leachate from contaminated sites or recharged via riverbank filtration (Regnery et al. 2011). In another German study, neither TCEP nor TCPP was removed during bank filtration, although TBEP was removed, which was attributed to their biodegradability (Stepien et al. 2013). In many countries, agricultural soils are amended with sewage sludge to increase the nutrient content of soils, yet there is very little control of the presence of organic contaminants in sludge,

which enter the environment during agronomic practices. The reason for this is that conventional wastewater treatment does not completely remove TCEP, TCPP, and TBEP (Cristale et al. 2016), but instead these compounds accumulate in sludge.

Concentrations of TCEP, TCPP, and TBEP in sludge ranged from 6.3 to 366 ngg⁻¹ in Chinese municipal WWTP's (Zeng et al. 2014), while their concentration ranged from 6.6 to 1900 µgkg⁻¹ in Swedish municipal WWTPs (Marklund et al. 2005), and they were among the main flame retardants detected in sewage sludge in Spain (Cristale and Lacorte 2013).

The use of sludge as a soil amendment in agriculture is of concern given that OPEs can either sorb into the soil and affect soil fauna, or desorb from soils, as observed for TCPP and TCEP, and potentially contaminate groundwater. There is therefore a pressing need to monitor the presence of OPE's in different types of soils in order to protect them and the water resources from contamination by these compounds.

5.2 CONCLUSION

The result of this study shows that there are varying degrees of concentration of Organophosphates esters in the soil sample extracted from car dismantling sites in the study area. Although, out of the thirteen OPEs analyzed, only a few number are predominantly and significantly recorded in the different location visited. The ones found in minute quantity can sediment over time or be washed by erosion into water bodies due to their high octanol-water partition coefficient which measures the degree to which they dissolve in water or other solvent leading to aquatic life poisoning and other harmful effects to life forms.

5.3 RECOMMENDATION

It is therefore, highly recommended that further research should be carried out periodically in soils of car dismantling within the study area of this research. Further research will reveal some characteristics of OPEs that are present in the study area such as biopersistency, bioaccumulation e.t.c. and subsequently advocate for it's replacement with other fire retardants which are harmless to life forms.

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